

Top 10 Read Article in Computer Science & Information Technology: September 2021

**International Journal of Computer Science and
Information Technology (IJCSIT)**

WJCI Indexed

ISSN: 0975-3826(online); 0975-4660 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit.html>

ONLINE LEARNING DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC, AND POSSIBILITY OF ADOPTING COMPUTER-BASED TEST

Rabea Emdas¹ and Ahmed Alruwaili²

**¹Faculty of Science, Engineering and Technology, Swinburne University of
Technology, Hawthorn, Victoria 3122, Australia**

**²Department of Computer Science and Information Technology, La Trobe
University, Bundoora, Victoria 3086, Australia.**

ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

E-learning, COVID-19, online education, Computer-Based Exams, Computer test.

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijsit/V13N4/13421ijsit01.pdf>

Volume Link : https://airccse.org/journal/ijsit2021_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Peia, L., and Wub, H.: 'Does online learning work better than offline learning in undergraduate medical education? A systematic review and meta-analysis', 2019 VOL. 24, 1666538.
- [2] Stone, C.: 'Online learning in Australian higher education: Opportunities, challenges and transformations'. *Student Success*, 2019,10, (2), pp. 1-11.
- [3] Shacham, M.: 'Computer-based exams in undergraduate engineering courses', *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, 1998, 6, (3), pp. 201-209.
- [4] Wingenbach, G.J.: 'Agriculture Students' Skills and Electronic Exams', *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 2000, 41, (1), pp. 69-78.
- [5] Mary, P.: 'The Effect of Using Item Parameters Calibrated from Paper Administrations in Computer Adaptive Test Administrations', *The Journal of Technology, Learning and Assessment*, 2007, 5, (7).
- [6] Goldberg, A.L., and Pedulla, J.J.: 'Performance Differences According to Test Mode and Computer Familiarity on a Practice Graduate Record Exam', *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 2016, 62, (6), pp. 1053-1067.
- [7] Randy Elliot, B., James, B., Andreas, O., Brent, S., Bruce, K., and Fred, Y.: 'Does it Matter if I Take My Mathematics Test on Computer? A Second Empirical Study of Mode Effects in NAEP', *The Journal of Technology, Learning and Assessment*, 2008, 6, (9).
- [8] Zilles C, West M, Mussulman D and Bretl T. Making testing less trying: Lessons learned from operating a Computer-Based Testing Facility. In 2018 IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference (FIE), pp. 1-9.
- [9] Morrison, B.B., Margulieux, L.E., Ericson, B., and Guzdial, M.: 'Subgoals help students solve Parsons problems', in Editor: 'Book Subgoals help students solve Parsons problems' (2016,edn.), pp. 42-47.
- [10] Zilles, C., Deloatch, R.T., Bailey, J., Khattar, B.B., Fagen, W., Heeren, C., Mussulman, D., and West, M.: 'Computerized testing: A vision and initial experiences', *age*, 2015, 26, pp.1.
- [11] Hainey, T., Connolly, T.M., Boyle, E.A., Wilson, A., and Razak, A.: 'A systematic literature review of games-based learning empirical evidence in primary education', *Computers & Education*, 2016, 102, pp. 202-223.
- [12] Palvia, S., Aeron, P., Gupta, P., Mahapatra, D., Parida, R., Rosner, R., and Sindhi, S.: 'Online education: Worldwide status, challenges, trends, and implications', *Journal of Global Information Technology Management*, 2018,21, (4), pp. 233-241.
- [13] Wright, N.: 'e-Learning and implications for New Zealand schools: A literature review', Ministry of Education, 2010.

- [14] Kaup, S., Jain, R., Shivalli, S., Pandey, S., and Kaup, S.: 'Sustaining academics during COVID-19 pandemic: the role of online teaching-learning', *Indian Journal of Ophthalmology*, 2020 Jun;68(6):1220.
- [15] Unger, S., and Meiran, W. R.: 'Student Attitudes towards Online Education during the COVID-19 Viral Outbreak of 2020: Distance Learning in a Time of Social Distance', *International Journal of Technology in Education and Science*, 2020,4, (4), pp. 256-66.
- [16] Seymour-Walsh AE, Weber A, and Bell A.: 'Pedagogical foundations to online lectures in health professions education', *Rural and Remote Health*. 2020 May 29;20(2):6038-.
- [17] Lorenza, L., and Carter, D.: 'Emergency online teaching during COVID-19: A case study of Australian tertiary students in teacher education and creative arts'. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*,2021,2, 100057.
- [18] Sodhar, I. N., Jalbani, A. H., Buller, A. H., and Sodhar, A. N.: 'Tools Used In Online Teaching and Learning through Lock-Down'. 2020, (8), pp. 36-40.
- [19] Frankel, R., Altschuler, A., George, S., Kinsman, J., Jimison, H., Robertson, N.R., and Hsu, J.: 'Effects of exam-room computing on clinician-patient communication: a longitudinal qualitative study', *J Gen Intern Med*, 2005, 20, (8), pp. 677-682.
- [20] Zilles, C.B., West, M., Herman, G.L., and Bretl, T.: 'Every University Should Have a Computer-Based Testing Facility', in Editor (Ed.)^(Eds.): 'Book Every University Should Have a Computer-Based Testing Facility' (2019, edn.), pp. 414-420.
- [21] Blumenstein, M.: 'Synergies of Learning Analytics and Learning Design: A Systematic Review of Student Outcomes', *Journal of Learning Analytics*, 2020, 7, (3), pp. 13-32.

SECURITY THREATS ON CLOUD COMPUTING VULNERABILITIES

Te-Shun Chou

**Department of Technology Systems, East Carolina University, Greenville, NC,
U.S.A.**

ABSTRACT

Clouds provide a powerful computing platform that enables individuals and organizations to perform variety levels of tasks such as: use of online storage space, adoption of business applications, development of customized computer software, and creation of a “realistic” network environment. In previous years, the number of people using cloud services has dramatically increased and lots of data has been stored in cloud computing environments. In the meantime, data breaches to cloud services are also increasing every year due to hackers who are always trying to exploit the security vulnerabilities of the architecture of cloud. In this paper, three cloud service models were compared; cloud security risks and threats were investigated based on the nature of the cloud service models. Real world cloud attacks were included to demonstrate the techniques that hackers used against cloud computing systems. In addition, countermeasures to cloud security breaches are presented.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud security threats and countermeasures, cloud service models

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/jcsit/5313iicsit06.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/iicsit2013_curr.html

REFERENCES

1. DataLossDB Open Security Foundation. <http://datalossdb.org/statistics>
2. Sophos Security Threat Report 2012. <http://www.sophos.com/>
3. Amazon.com Server Said to Have Been Used in Sony Attack, May 2011. <http://www.bloomberg.com/news/2011-05-13/sony-network-said-to-have-been-invaded-by-hackersusing-amazon-com-server.html>
4. D. Jamil and H. Zaki, "[Security Issues in Cloud Computing and Countermeasures](#)," International Journal of Engineering Science and Technology, Vol. 3 No. 4, pp. 2672-2676, April 2011.
5. K. Zunnurhain and S. Vrbsky, "[Security Attacks and Solutions in Clouds](#)," 2nd IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing Technology and Science, Indianapolis, December 2010.
6. W. A. Jansen, "Cloud Hooks: Security and Privacy Issues in Cloud Computing," 44th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, pp. 1–10, Koloa, Hawaii, January 2011.
7. T. Roth, "[Breaking Encryptions Using GPU Accelerated Cloud Instances](#)," Black Hat Technical Security Conference, 2011.
8. CERT Coordination Center, Denial of Service. http://www.packetstormsecurity.org/distributed/denial_of_service.html
9. M. Jensen, J. Schwenk, N. Gruschka, and L. L. Iacono, "[On Technical Security Issues in Cloud Computing](#)," IEEE International Conference in Cloud Computing, pp. 109-116, Bangalore, 2009.
10. Thunder in the Cloud: \$6 Cloud-Based Denial-of-Service Attack, August 2010. http://blogs.computerworld.com/16708/thunder_in_the_cloud_6_cloud_based_denial_of_service_attack
11. DDoS Attack Rains Down on Amazon Cloud, October 2009. http://www.theregister.co.uk/2009/10/05/amazon_bitbucket_outage/
12. 2011 CyberSecurity Watch Survey, CERT Coordination Center at Carnegie Mellon University.
13. D. Catteddu and G. Hogben, "[Cloud Computing Benefits, Risks and Recommendations for Information Security](#)," The European Network and Information Security Agency (ENISA), November 2009.

14. Insider Threats Related to Cloud Computing, CERT, July 2012. <http://www.cert.org/>
15. Data Breach Trends & Stats, Symantec, 2012. <http://www.indefenseofdata.com/data-breach-trendsstats/>
16. 2012 Has Delivered Her First Giant Data Breach, January 2012. <http://www.infosecisland.com/blogview/19432-2012-Has-Delivered-Her-First-Giant-DataBreach.html>
17. A Few Wrinkles Are Etching Facebook, Other Social Sites, USA Today, 2011. http://www.usatoday.com/printedition/life/20090115/socialnetworking15_st.art.html
18. An Update on LinkedIn Member Passwords Compromised, LinkedIn Blog, June, 2012. <http://blog.linkedin.com/2012/06/06/linkedin-member-passwords-compromised/>
19. Dropbox: Yes, We Were Hacked, August 2012. <http://gigaom.com/cloud/dropbox-yes-we-werehacked/>
20. Web Based Attacks, Symantec White Paper, February 2009.
21. Symantec Internet Security Threat Report, 2011 Trends, Vol. 17, April 2012.
22. P. P. Ramgonda and R. R. Mudholkar, “[Cloud Market Cogitation and Techniques to Averting SQL Injection for University Cloud](#),” International Journal of Computer Technology and Applications, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp. 1217-1224, January, 2012.
23. A. S. Choudhary and M. L. Dhore, “[CIDT: Detection of Malicious Code Injection Attacks on Web Application](#),” International Journal of Computer Applications, Vol. 52, No. 2, pp. 19-26, August 2012.
24. Web Application Attack Report For The Second Quarter of 2012. <http://www.firehost.com/company/newsroom/web-application-attack-report-second-quarter-2012>
25. Visitors to Sony PlayStation Website at Risk of Malware Infection, July 2008. <http://www.sophos.com/en-us/press-office/press-releases/2008/07/playstation.aspx>
26. N. Provos, M. A. Rajab, and P. Mavrommatis, “Cybercrime 2.0: When the Cloud Turns Dark,” ACM Communications, Vol. 52, No. 4, pp. 42–47, 2009.
27. S. S. Rajan, Cloud Security Series | SQL Injection and SaaS, Cloud Computing Journal, November 2010.

28. Researchers Demo Cloud Security Issue With Amazon AWS Attack, October 2011. http://www.pcworld.idg.com.au/article/405419/researchers_demo_cloud_security_is_sue_amazon_aws_attack/
29. M. McIntosh and P. Austel, "XML Signature Element Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," 2005 workshop on Secure web services, ACM Press, New York, NY, pp. 20–27, 2005.
30. N. Gruschka and L. L. Iacono, "[Vulnerable Cloud: SOAP Message Security Validation Revisited](#)," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, Los Angeles, 2009.
31. A. Tripathi and A. Mishra, "Cloud Computing Security Considerations Interface," 2011 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing, Xi'an, China, September 2011.
32. H. C. Li, P. H. Liang, J. M. Yang, and S. J. Chen, "Analysis on Cloud-Based Security Vulnerability Assessment," IEEE International Conference on E-Business Engineering, pp.490-494, November 2010.
33. Amazon: Hey Spammers, Get Off My Cloud!http://voices.washingtonpost.com/securityfix/2008/07/amazon_hey_spammers_get_off_my.html
34. W. Jansen and T. Grance, "Guidelines on Security and Privacy in Public Cloud Computing," Computer Security Division, Information Technology Laboratory, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Special Publication 800-144, December 2011.
35. Tackling the Insider Threat <http://www.bankinfosecurity.com/blogs.php?postID=140>
36. "Cloud Security Risks and Solutions," White Paper, BalaBit IT Security, July 2010.
37. S. J. Stolfo, M. B. Salem, and A. D. Keromytis, "Fog computing: Mitigating Insider Data Theft Attacks in the Cloud," IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy Workshops, pp. 125-128, San Francisco, CA, 2012.
38. M. Jensen, C. Meyer, J. Somorovsky, and J. Schwenk, "On the Effectiveness of XML Schema Validation for Countering XML Signature Wrapping Attacks," First International Workshop on Securing Services on the Cloud, Milan, Italy, September 2011.
39. S. Gajek, M. Jensen, L. Liao, and J. Schwenk, "Analysis of Signature Wrapping Attacks and Countermeasures," IEEE International Conference on Web Services, pp. 575–582, Miami, Florida, July 2009

DATA WAREHOUSE AND BIG DATA INTEGRATION

**Sonia Ordoñez Salinas and Alba Consuelo Nieto Lemus Faculty of Engineering, Distrial
F.J.C University, Bogotá, Colombia**

ABSTRACT

Big Data triggered furthered an influx of research and prospective on concepts and processes pertaining previously to the Data Warehouse field. Some conclude that Data Warehouse as such will disappear; others present Big Data as the natural Data Warehouse evolution (perhaps without identifying a clear division between the two); and finally, some others pose a future of convergence, partially exploring the possible integration of both. In this paper, we revise the underlying technological features of Big Data and Data Warehouse, highlighting their differences and areas of convergence. Even when some differences exist, both technologies could (and should) be integrated because they both aim at the same purpose: data exploration and decision making support. We explore some convergence strategies, based on the common elements in both technologies. We present a revision of the state-of-the-art in integration proposals from the point of view of the purpose, methodology, architecture and underlying technology, highlighting the common elements that support both technologies that may serve as a starting point for full integration and we propose a proposal of integration between the two technologies.

KEYWORDS

Big Data, Data Warehouse, Integration, Hadoop, NoSql, MapReduce, 7V's, 3C's, M&G

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijcsit/V9N2/9217ijcsit01.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2017_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Bedi, V. Jindal, and A. Gautam, “Beginning with Big Data Simplified,” 2014.
- [2] R. Kimball, M. Ross, W. Thorthwaite, B. Becker, and M. J, The Data Warehouse Lifecycle Toolkit, 2nd Edition. 2008.
- [3] C. Todman, Designing A Data Warehouse: Supporting Customer Relationship Management. 2001.
- [4] W. H. Inmon, Building the Data Warehouse, 4th Edition. 2005. [5] “Oracle Database 12c for Data Warehousing and Big Data .” [Online]. Available: <http://www.oracle.com/technetwork/database/bi-datawarehousing/data-warehousing-wp-12c1896097.pdf>. [Accessed: 09-Sep-2015].
- [6] M. Cox and D. Ellsworth, “Application-Controlled Demand Paging for Out-of-Core Visualization,” 1997. [Online]. Available: <http://www.nas.nasa.gov/assets/pdf/techreports/1997/nas-97-010.pdf>. [Accessed: 09-Apr-2015].
- [7] S. Chaudhuri and U. Dayal, “An overview of data warehousing and OLAP technology,” ACM SIGMOD Rec., vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 65–74, 1997. [8] T. Maioreescu, “General Information on Business Intelligence,” pp. 294–297, 2010. [9] “Data Warehouses and OLAP: Concepts, Architectures and Solutions: 9781599043647: Library and Information Science Books | IGI Global.” .
- [10] Y. Demchenko, C. De Laat, and P. Membrey, “Defining Architecture Components of the Big Data Ecosystem,” Collab. Technol. Syst. (CTS), 2014 Int. Conf., pp. 104–112, 2014.
- [11] G. NBD-PWG, “ISO/IEC JTC 1 Study Group on Big Data,” 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://bigdatawg.nist.gov/cochairs.php>. [Accessed: 24-Oct-2015].
- [12] D. L. W.H. Inmon, Data Architecture: A Primer for the Data Scientist: Big Data, Data Warehouse and Data Vault. Amsterdam,Boston: Elsevier, 2014.
- [13] G. N. W.H. Inmon, Derek Strauss, DW 2.0: The Architecture for the Next Generation of Data Warehousing (Morgan Kaufman Series in Data Management Systems) (: : Books. Burlington, USA: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Inc., 2008.
- [14] R. Kimball, “The Evolving Role of the Enterprise Data Warehouse in the Era of Big Data Analytics,” Kimball Gr., 2011.
- [15] M. Muntean and T. Surcel, “Agile BI - The Future of BI,” Inform. Econ., vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 114–124, 2013.
- [16] D. Agrawal, “The Reality of Real-Time Business Intelligence,” in Business Intelligence for the RealTime Enterprise, vol. 27 , M. Castellanos, U. Dayal, and T. Sellis, Eds. Springer Berlin Heidelberg , 2009, pp. 75–88.
- [17] R. Castillo, J. Morata, and L. del Arbol, “Operational Data Store (ODS) - 933.pdf,” Actas del III taller nacional de minería de datos y aprendizaje, pp. 359–365, 2005.
- [18] S. YiChuan and X. Yao, “Research of Real-time Data Warehouse Storage Strategy Based on Multilevel Caches,” Phys. Procedia, vol. 25, no. 0, pp. 2315–2321, 2012.
- [19] A. Ma. P. Díaz-zorita, “Evaluación de la herramienta de código libre Apache Hadoop,” Universidad Carlos III de Madrid Escuela Politécnica Superior, 2011.
- [20] R. Kimball, “Newly Emerging Best Practices for Big Data,” Kimball Group, p. 14, 2012.

- [21] M. Maier, "Towards a Big Data Reference Architecture," no. October, pp. 1–144, 2013.
- [22] O. Corporation, "ORACLE ENTERPRISE ARCHITECTURE WHITE PAPER. An Enterprise Architect's Guide to Big Data," no. February, 2015.
- [23] F. Kramer, H. Muller, and K. Turowski, "Acceleration of Single Inserts for Columnar Databases -- An Experiment on Data Import Performance Using SAP HANA," in Signal-Image Technology and Internet-Based Systems (SITIS), 2014 Tenth International Conference on, 2014, pp. 672–676.
- [24] M. R. Patil and F. Thia, Pentaho for Big Data Analytics, vol. 2013. PACKT PUBLISHING, 2013.
- [25] S. G. Manikandan and S. Ravi, "Big Data Analysis Using Apache Hadoop," in IT Convergence and Security (ICITCS), 2014 International Conference on , 2014, pp. 1–4.
- [26] J. Nandimath, E. Banerjee, A. Patil, P. Kakade, and S. Vaidya, "Big data analysis using Apache Hadoop," 2013 IEEE 14th Int. Conf. Inf. Reuse Integr., pp. 700–703, 2013.
- [27] A. Katal, M. Wazid, and R. H. Goudar, "Big data: Issues, challenges, tools and Good practices," in Contemporary Computing (IC3), 2013 Sixth International Conference on , 2013, pp. 404–409.
- [28] A. Pal and S. Agrawal, "An Experimental Approach Towards Big Data for Analyzing Memory Utilization on a Hadoop cluster using HDFS and MapReduce .," pp. 442–447, 2014.
- [29] R. Zhang, D. Hildebrand, and R. Tewari, "In unity there is strength: Showcasing a unified big data platform with MapReduce Over both object and file storage," in Big Data (Big Data), 2014 IEEE International Conference on , 2014, pp. 960–966.
- [30] "Welcome to Apache™ Hadoop®!" [Online]. Available: <https://hadoop.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [31] "HDFS Architecture Guide." [Online]. Available: http://hadoop.apache.org/docs/r1.2.1/hdfs_design.html. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [32] S. Brin and L. Page, "The Anatomy of a Large-Scale Hypertextual Web Search Engine," in Computer Networks and ISDN Systems, 1998, pp. 107–117. [
- [33] D. Garlasu, V. Sandulescu, I. Halcu, G. Neculoiu, O. Grigoriu, M. Marinescu, and V. Marinescu, "A big data implementation based on Grid computing," in Roedunet International Conference (RoEduNet), 2013 11th, 2013, pp. 1–4.
- [34] A. Jorgensen, C. Price, B. Mitchell, and J. Rowlan, Microsoft Big Data Solutions. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2014.
- [35] R. T. Kaushik, M. Bhandarkar, and K. Nahrstedt, "Evaluation and Analysis of GreenHDFS: A SelfAdaptive, Energy-Conserving Variant of the Hadoop Distributed File System," in Cloud Computing Technology and Science (CloudCom), 2010 IEEE Second International Conference on, 2010, pp. 274–287.
- [36] J. G. Shanahan and L. Dai, "Large Scale Distributed Data Science Using Apache Spark," in Proceedings of the 21th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, 2015, pp. 2323–2324.
- [37] R. S. Xin, J. Rosen, M. Zaharia, M. J. Franklin, S. Shenker, and I. Stoica, "Shark: SQL and Rich Analytics at Scale," in Proceedings of the 2013 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on

Management of Data, 2013, pp. 13–24.

- [38] J. Li, J. Wu, X. Yang, and S. Zhong, “Optimizing MapReduce Based on Locality of K-V Pairs and Overlap between Shuffle and Local Reduce,” in *Parallel Processing (ICPP)*, 2015 44th International Conference on, 2015, pp. 939–948.
- [39] E. Brewer, “CAP Twelve Years Later: How the ‘Rules’ Have Changed,” *InfoQ*, 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://www.infoq.com/articles/cap-twelve-years-later-how-the-rules-have-changed>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [40] G. Vaish, *Getting started with NoSQL*. 2013.
- [41] V. N. Gudivada, D. Rao, and V. V. Raghavan, “NoSQL Systems for Big Data Management,” 2014 IEEE World Congr. Serv., pp. 190–197, 2014.
- [42] Cassandra, “The Apache Cassandra Project,” <http://cassandra.apache.org>, 2010. [Online]. Available: <http://cassandra.apache.org/>.
- [43] D. Borthakur, “Petabyte Scale Databases and Storage Systems at Facebook,” in *Proceedings of the 2013 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data*, 2013, pp. 1267–1268.
- [44] J. Huang, X. Ouyang, J. Jose, M. Wasi-ur-Rahman, H. Wang, M. Luo, H. Subramoni, C. Murthy, and D. K. Panda, “High-Performance Design of HBase with RDMA over InfiniBand,” in *Parallel*
- [45] G. Weintraub, “Dynamo and BigTable - Review and comparison,” *Electr. Electron. Eng. Isr. (IEEEI)*, 2014 IEEE 28th Conv., pp. 1–5, 2
- [46] D. Pereira, P. Oliveira, and F. Rodrigues, “Data warehouses in MongoDB vs SQL Server: A comparative analysis of the querie performance,” in *Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI)*, 2015 10th Iberian Conference on, 2015, pp. 1–7.
- [47] K. Dehdouh, F. Bentayeb, O. Boussaid, and N. Kabachi, “Columnar NoSQL CUBE: Agregation operator for columnar NoSQL data warehouse,” in *Systems, Man and Cybernetics (SMC)*, 2014 IEEE International Conference on, 2014, pp. 3828–3833.
- [48] Y. Liu and T. M. Vitolo, “Graph Data Warehouse: Steps to Integrating Graph Databases Into the Traditional Conceptual Structure of a Data Warehouse,” in *Big Data (BigData Congress)*, 2013 IEEE International Congress on, 2013, pp. 433–434.
- [49] M. Chevalier, M. El Malki, A. Kopliku, O. Teste, and R. Tournier, “Benchmark for OLAP on NoSQL technologies comparing NoSQL multidimensional data warehousing solutions,” in *Research Challenges in Information Science (RCIS)*, 2015 IEEE 9th International Conference on, 2015, pp. 480–485.
- [50] F. Färber, S. K. Cha, J. Primsch, C. Bornhövd, S. Sigg, and W. Lehner, “SAP HANA Database: Data Management for Modern Business Applications,” *SIGMOD Rec.*, vol. 40, no. 4, pp. 45–51, 2012.
- [51] K. M. A. Hasan, M. T. Omar, S. M. M. Ahsan, and N. Nahar, “Chunking implementation of extendible array to handle address space overflow for large multidimensional data sets,” in *Electrical Information and Communication Technology (EICT)*, 2013 International Conference on, 2014, pp. 1– 6.
- [52] S. Müller and H. Plattner, “An In-depth Analysis of Data Aggregation Cost Factors in a Columnar Inmemory Database,” in *Proceedings of the Fifteenth International Workshop on Data Warehousing and OLAP*, 2012, pp. 65–72.

- [53] H. Plattner, "A Common Database Approach for OLTP and OLAP Using an In-memory Column Database," in Proceedings of the 2009 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data, 2009, pp. 1–2.
- [54] J. Schaffner, A. Bog, J. Krüger, and A. Zeier, "A Hybrid Row-Column OLTP Database Architecture for Operational Reporting," in Business Intelligence for the Real-Time Enterprise SE - 5, vol. 27, M. Castellanos, U. Dayal, and T. Sellis, Eds. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009, pp. 61–74.
- [55] V. K. Vavilapalli, A. C. Murthy, C. Douglas, S. Agarwal, M. Konar, R. Evans, T. Graves, J. Lowe, H. Shah, S. Seth, B. Saha, C. Curino, O. O'Malley, S. Radia, B. Reed, and E. Baldeschwieler, "Apache Hadoop YARN: Yet Another Resource Negotiator," in Proceedings of the 4th Annual Symposium on Cloud Computing, 2013, pp. 5:1–5:16.
- [56] "Apache Pig Philosophy." [Online]. Available: <http://pig.apache.org/philosophy.html>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [57] "Architecture - Apache Drill." [Online]. Available: <http://drill.apache.org/architecture/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [58] "Storm, distributed and fault-tolerant realtime computation." [Online]. Available: <https://storm.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [59] "Apache Hive TM." [Online]. Available: <https://hive.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015]. [60] "Sqoop -." [Online]. Available: <http://sqoop.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [61] "Impala." [Online]. Available: <http://www.cloudera.com/content/cloudera/en/products-and-services/cdh/impala.html>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [62] "Apache Thrift - Home." [Online]. Available: <https://thrift.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [63] "Apache ZooKeeper - Home." [Online]. Available: <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>. [Accessed: 26-Mar-2015].
- [64] D. Borthakur, J. Gray, J. Sen Sarma, K. Muthukkaruppan, N. Spiegelberg, H. Kuang, K. Ranganathan, D. Molkov, A. Menon, S. Rash, R. Schmidt, and A. Aiyer, "Apache Hadoop Goes Realtime at Facebook," in Proceedings of the 2011 ACM SIGMOD International Conference on Management of Data, 2011, pp. 1071–1080.
- [65] B. Ghit, A. Iosup, and D. Epema, "Towards an Optimized Big Data Processing System," in Cluster, Cloud and Grid Computing (CCGrid), 2013 13th IEEE/ACM International Symposium on, 2013, pp. 83–86.
- [66] P. Agarwal, G. Shroff, and P. Malhotra, "Approximate Incremental Big-Data Harmonization," in Big Data (BigData Congress), 2013 IEEE International Congress on, 2013, pp. 118–125.
- [67] Y. Elshater, P. Martin, D. Rope, M. McRoberts, and C. Statchuk, "A Study of Data Locality in YARN," 2015 IEEE Int. Congr. Big Data, pp. 174–181, 2015.
- [68] A. H. B. James Manyika, Michael Chui, Brad Brown, Jacques Bughin, Richard Dobbs, Charles Roxburgh, "Big data: The next frontier for innovation, competition, and productivity," McKinsey Glob. Inst., no. June, p. 156, 2011.
- [69] J. S. Marron, "Big Data in context and robustness against heterogeneity," Econom. Stat., vol. 2, pp. 73–80, 2017.

- [70] L. Kugler, "What Happens When Big Data Blunders?," *Commun. ACM*, vol. 59, no. 6, pp. 15–16, 2016.
- [71] S. Sagiroglu, R. Terzi, Y. Canbay, and I. Colak, "Big data issues in smart grid systems," in 2016 IEEE International Conference on Renewable Energy Research and Applications (ICRERA), 2016, pp. 1007–1012.
- [72] A. Gandomi and M. Haider, "Beyond the hype: Big data concepts, methods, and analytics," *Int. J. Inf. Manage.*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 137–144, 2015.
- [73] Jameela Al-Jaroodi, Brandon Hollein, Nader Mohamed, "Applying software engineering processes for big data analytics applications development", *Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC) 2017 IEEE 7th Annual*, pp. 1-7, 2017

CLUSTERING ALGORITHM FOR A HEALTHCARE DATASET USING SILHOUETTE SCORE VALUE

Godwin Ogbuabor¹ and Ugwoke, F. N²

¹ School of Computer Science, University of Lincoln, United Kingdom

²Department of Computer Science, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The huge amount of healthcare data, coupled with the need for data analysis tools has made data mining interesting research areas. Data mining tools and techniques help to discover and understand hidden patterns in a dataset which may not be possible by mainly visualization of the data. Selecting appropriate clustering method and optimal number of clusters in healthcare data can be confusing and difficult most times. Presently, a large number of clustering algorithms are available for clustering healthcare data, but it is very difficult for people with little knowledge of data mining to choose suitable clustering algorithms. This paper aims to analyze clustering techniques using healthcare dataset, in order to determine suitable algorithms which can bring the optimized group clusters. Performances of two clustering algorithms (Kmeans and DBSCAN) were compared using Silhouette score values. Firstly, we analyzed K-means algorithm using different number of clusters (K) and different distance metrics. Secondly, we analyzed DBSCAN algorithm using different minimum number of points required to form a cluster (minPts) and different distance metrics. The experimental result indicates that both K-means and DBSCAN algorithms have strong intra-cluster cohesion and inter-cluster separation. Based on the analysis, K-means algorithm performed better compare to DBSCAN algorithm in terms of clustering accuracy and execution time.

KEYWORDS

Dataset, Clustering, Healthcare data, Silhouette score value, K-means, DBSCAN

For More Details : <https://airceonline.com/iicsit/V10N2/10218iicsit03.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/iicsit2018_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Alsayat, A., & El-Sayed, H. (2016). Efficient genetic K-Means clustering for health care knowledge discovery. In *Software Engineering Research, Management and Applications (SERA)*, 2016 IEEE 14th International Conference on (pp. 45-52). IEEE.
- [2] Balasubramanian, T., & Umarani, R. (2012, March). An analysis on the impact of fluoride in human health (dental) using clustering data mining technique. In *Pattern Recognition, Informatics and Medical Engineering (PRIME)*, 2012 International Conference on (pp. 370-375). IEEE.
- [3] Banu G. Rasitha & Jamala J.H.Bousal (2015). Predicting Heart Attack using Fuzzy C Means Clustering Algorithm. *International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJLTET)*.
- [4] Banu, M. N., & Gomathy, B. (2014). Disease forecasting system using data mining methods. In *Intelligent Computing Applications (ICICA)*, 2014 International Conference on (pp. 130-133). IEEE.
- [5] Belciug, S. (2009). Patients length of stay grouping using the hierarchical clustering algorithm. *Annals of the University of Craiova-Mathematics and Computer Science Series*, 36(2), 79-84.
- [6] Belciug, S., Salem, A. B., Gorunescu, F., & Gorunescu, M. (2010, November). Clustering-based approach for detecting breast cancer recurrence. In *Intelligent Systems Design and Applications (ISDA)*, 2010 10th International Conference on (pp. 533-538). IEEE.
- [7] Bruno, G., Cerquitelli, T., Chiusano, S., & Xiao, X. (2014). A clustering-based approach to analyse examinations for diabetic patients. In *Healthcare Informatics (ICHI)*, 2014 IEEE International Conference on (pp. 45-50). IEEE.
- [8] DeFreitas, K., & Bernard, M. (2015). Comparative performance analysis of clustering techniques in educational data mining. *IADIS International Journal on Computer Science & Information Systems*, 10(2).
- [9] Escudero, J., Zajicek, J. P., & Ifeachor, E. (2011). Early detection and characterization of Alzheimer's disease in clinical scenarios using Bioprofile concepts and K-means. In *Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society, EMBC, 2011 Annual International Conference of the IEEE* (pp. 6470-6473). IEEE.
- [10] Han, J., Kamber, M., & Pei, J. (2012). *Cluster Analysis-10: Basic Concepts and Methods*.
- [11] Ibrahim, N. H., Mustapha, A., Rosli, R., & Helmee, N. H. (2013). A hybrid model of hierarchical clustering and decision tree for rule-based classification of diabetic patients. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology (IJET)*, 5(5), 3986-91.
- [12] Jabel K. Merlin & Srividhya (2016). Performance analysis of clustering algorithms on heart dataset. *International Journal of Modern Computer Science*, 5(4), 113-117.
- [13] Kar Amit Kumar, Shailesh Kumar Patel & Rajkishor Yadav (2016). A Comparative Study & Performance Evaluation of Different Clustering Techniques in Data Mining. *ACEIT Conference Proceeding*.
- [14] Lv, Y., Ma, T., Tang, M., Cao, J., Tian, Y., Al-Dhelaan, A., & Al-Rodhaan, M. (2016). An efficient and scalable density-based clustering algorithm for datasets with complex structures. *Neurocomputing*, 171, 9-22.

- [15] Malli, S., Nagesh, H. R., & Joshi, H. G. (2014). A Study on Rural Health care Data sets using Clustering Algorithms. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications*, 3(8), 517-520.
- [16] Maulik, U., & Bandyopadhyay, S. (2002). Performance evaluation of some clustering algorithms and validity indices. *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 24(12), 1650-1654.
- [17] Na, S., Xumin, L., & Yong, G. (2010, April). Research on k-means clustering algorithm: An improved k-means clustering algorithm. In *Intelligent Information Technology and Security Informatics (IITSI), 2010 Third International Symposium on* (pp. 63-67). IEEE.
- [18] Paul, R., & Hoque, A. S. M. L. (2010, July). Clustering medical data to predict the likelihood of diseases. In *Digital Information Management (ICDIM), 2010 Fifth International Conference on* (pp. 44-49). IEEE.
- [19] Pham, D. T., Dimov, S. S., & Nguyen, C. D. (2005). Selection of K in K-means clustering. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part C: Journal of Mechanical Engineering Science*, 219(1), 103-119.
- [20] R.Nithya & P.Manikandan & D.Ramyachitra (2015); Analysis of clustering technique for the diabetes dataset using the training set parameter. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering* Vol. 4, Issue 9.
- [21] Sagar, H. K., & Sharma, V. (2014). Error Evaluation on K-Means and Hierarchical Clustering with Effect of Distance Functions for Iris Dataset. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 86(16).
- [22] Shah, G. H., Bhensdadia, C. K., & Ganatra, A. P. (2012). An empirical evaluation of density-based clustering techniques. *International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering (IJSCE)* ISSN, 22312307, 216-223.
- [23] Tan, P. N., Steinbach, M., & Kumar, V. (2013). *Data mining cluster analysis: basic concepts and algorithms. Introduction to data mining.*
- [24] Tomar, D., & Agarwal, S. (2013). A survey on Data Mining approaches for Healthcare. *International Journal of Bio-Science and Bio-Technology*, 5(5), 241-266.
- [25] Vijayarani, S., & Sudha, S. (2015). An efficient clustering algorithm for predicting diseases from hemogram blood test samples. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 8(17).
- [26] Zheng, B., Yoon, S. W., & Lam, S. S. (2014). Breast cancer diagnosis based on feature extraction using a hybrid of K-means and support vector machine algorithms. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 41(4), 1476-1482

DATA MINING MODEL PERFORMANCE OF SALES PREDICTIVE ALGORITHMS BASED ON RAPIDMINER WORKFLOWS

Alessandro Massaro, Vincenzo Maritati, Angelo Galiano

Dyrecta Lab, IT research Laboratory, via Vescovo Simplicio, 45, 70014 Conversano (BA), Italy

ABSTRACT

By applying RapidMiner workflows has been processed a dataset originated from different data files, and containing information about the sales over three years of a large chain of retail stores. Subsequently, has been constructed a Deep Learning model performing a predictive algorithm suitable for sales forecasting. This model is based on artificial neural network –ANN- algorithm able to learn the model starting from sales historical data and by pre-processing the data. The best built model uses a multilayer neural network together with an “optimized operator” able to find automatically the best parameter setting of the implemented algorithm. In order to prove the best performing predictive model, other machine learning algorithms have been tested. The performance comparison has been performed between Support Vector Machine –SVM-, k-Nearest Neighbor k-NN-, Gradient Boosted Trees, Decision Trees, and Deep Learning algorithms. The comparison of the degree of correlation between real and predicted values, the average absolute error and the relative average error proved that ANN exhibited the best performance. The Gradient Boosted Trees approach represents an alternative approach having the second best performance. The case of study has been developed within the framework of an industry project oriented on the integration of high performance data mining models able to predict sales using –ERP- and customer relationship management –CRM- tools.

KEYWORDS

RapidMiner, Neural Network, Deep Learning, Gradient Boosted Trees, Data Mining Performance, Sales Prediction.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijcsit/V10N3/10318ijcsit03.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2018_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Penpece D., & Elma O. E. (2014) “Predicting Sales Revenue by Using Artificial Neural Network in Grocery Retailing Industry: A Case Study in Turkey”, *International Journal of Trade Economics and Finance*, Vol. 5, No. 5, pp435-440.
- [2] Thiesing F. M., & Vornberger, O. (1997) “Sales Forecasting Using Neural Networks”, *IEEE Proceedings ICNN’97, Houston, Texas, 9-12 June 1997*, pp2125-2128.
- [3] Zhang, G. P. (2003) “Time series forecasting using a hybrid ARIMA and neural network model”, *Neurocomputing*, Vol. 50, pp159–175.
- [4] Sharma, A., & Panigrahi, P. K. (2011) “Neural Network based Approach for Predicting Customer Churn in Cellular Network Services”, *International Journal of Computer Applications*, Vol. 27, No.11, pp0975–8887.
- [5] Kamakura, W., Mela, C. F., Ansari A., & al. (2005) ” Choice Models and Customer Relationship Management,” *Marketing Letters*, Vol. 16, No.3/4, pp279–291.
- [6] Smith, K. A., & Gupta, J. N. D. (2000) “Neural Networks in Business: Techniques and Applications for the Operations Researcher,” *Computers & Operations Research*, Vol. 27, No. 11–12, pp1023-1044.
- [7] Chattopadhyay, M., Dan, P. K., Majumdar, S., & Chakraborty, P. S. (2012) “Application of Artificial Neural Network in Market Segmentation: A Review on Recent Trends,” *Management Science Letters*, Vol. 2, pp425-438.
- [8] Berry, J. A. M., & Linoff, G. S. (2004) “Data Mining Techniques For Marketing, Sales, and Customer Relationship Management”, *Wiley*, Second Edition.
- [9] Buttle, F. (2009) “Customer Relationship Management Concepts and Technologies”, *Elsevier*, Second Edition.
- [10] Thomassey, S. (2014) “Sales Forecasting in Apparel and Fashion Industry: A Review”, *Springer*, chapter 2.
- [11] Massaro, A. Barbuzzi, D., Vitti, V., Galiano, A., Aruci, M., Pirlo, G. (2016) “Predictive Sales Analysis According to the Effect of Weather”, *Proceeding of the 2nd International Conference on Recent Trends and Applications in Computer Science and Information Technology*, Tirana, Albania, November 18 - 19, pp53-55.
- [12] Parsons, A.G. (2001), “The Association between Daily Weather and Daily Shopping Patterns”, *Australasian Marketing Journal*, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp78–84. [13] Steele, A.T., (1951) “Weather’s Effect on the Sales of a Department Store”, *Journal of Marketing* Vol. 15, No. 4, pp436–443.
- [14] Murray, K. B., Di Muro, F., Finn, A., & Leszczyc, P. P. (2010) “The Effect of Weather on Consumer Spending”, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, Vol. 17, No.6, pp512-520.
- [15] Massaro, A., Galiano, A., Barbuzzi, D., Pellicani, L., Birardi, G., Romagno, D. D., & Frulli, L., (2017) “Joint Activities of Market Basket Analysis and Product Facing for Business Intelligence oriented on Global Distribution Market: examples of data mining applications,” *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technologies*, Vol. 8, No.2 , pp178-183.

- [16] Aguinis, H., Forcum, L. E., & Joo, H. (2013) "Using Market Basket Analysis in Management Research," *Journal of Management*, Vol. 39, No. 7, pp1799-1824.
- [17] Štulec, I, Petljak, K., & Kukor, A. (2016) "The Role of Store Layout and Visual Merchandising in Food Retailing", *European Journal of Economics and Business Studies*, Vol. 4, No. 1, pp139-152.
- [18] Otha, M. & Higuci, Y. (2013) "Study on Design of Supermarket Store Layouts: the Principle of "Sales Magnet"", *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology*, Vol. 7, No. 1, pp209-212.
- [19] Shallu, & Gupta, S. (2013) "Impact of Promotional Activities on Consumer Buying Behavior: A Study of Cosmetic Industry", *International Journal of Commerce, Business and Management (IJCBM)*, Vol. 2, No.6, pp379-385.
- [20] Al Essa, A. & Bach, C. (2014)" Data Mining and Knowledge Management for Marketing", *International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research*, Vol. 2, No. 2, pp321-328.
- [21] Kotu, V., & Deshpande B. (2015) "Predictive Analytics and Data Mining- Concepts and Practice with RapidMiner" Elsevier.
- [22] Wimmer, H., Powell, L. M. (2015) "A Comparison of Open Source Tools for Data Science", *Proceedings of the Conference on Information Systems Applied Research*. Wilmington, North Carolina USA.
- [23] Al-Khoder, A., Harmouch, H., "Evaluating Four Of The most Popular Open Source and Free Data Mining Tools", *International Journal of Academic Scientific Research*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp13-23.
- [24] Gulli, A., & Pal, S. (2017) "Deep Learning with Keras- Implement neural networks with Keras on Theano and TensorFlow," Birmingham -Mumbai Packt book, ISBN 978-1-78712-842-2.
- [25] Kovalev, V., Kalinovsky, A., & Kovalev, S. (2016) "Deep Learning with Theano, Torch, Caffe, TensorFlow, and deeplearning4j: which one is the best in speed and accuracy?" *Proceeding of XIII Int. Conf. on Pattern Recognition and Information Processing*, 3-5 October, Minsk, Belarus State University, pp99-103.
- [26] "Walmart Recruiting - Store Sales Forecasting" 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.kaggle.com/c/walmart-recruiting-store-sales-forecasting/data>
- [27] Huang, H.-C. & Hou, C.-I.. (2017) "Tourism Demand Forecasting Model Using Neural Network", *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)*, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp19- 29.
- [28] Kalyani, J., Bharathi, H. N., & Rao, J. (2016) "Stock Trend Prediction Using News Sentiment Analysis", *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)*, Vol. 8, No. 3, pp67-76.

INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM CLASSIFICATION USING DIFFERENT MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS ON KDD-99 AND NSL-KDD DATASETS - A REVIEW PAPER

Ravipati Rama Devi¹ and Munther Abualkibash²

¹Department of Computer Science, Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti, Michigan, USA

²School of Information Security and Applied Computing, Eastern Michigan University, Ypsilanti, Michigan, USA

ABSTRACT

Intrusion Detection System (IDS) has been an effective way to achieve higher security in detecting malicious activities for the past couple of years. Anomaly detection is an intrusion detection system. Current anomaly detection is often associated with high false alarm rates and only moderate accuracy and detection rates because it's unable to detect all types of attacks correctly. An experiment is carried out to evaluate the performance of the different machine learning algorithms using KDD-99 Cup and NSL-KDD datasets. Results show which approach has performed better in term of accuracy, detection rate with reasonable false alarm rate.

KEYWORDS

Intrusion Detection System, KDD-99 cup, NSL-KDD, Machine learning algorithms

For More Details : <https://aireconline.com/ijcsit/V11N3/11319ijcsit06.pdf>

Volume Link : http://aircse.org/journal/ijcsit2019_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] “DARPA98 attack description and schedule,” <https://www.ll.mit.edu/ideval/docs/attacks.html>, 1998, retrieved December 15, 2016.
- [2] L. Breiman, J. H. Friedman, R. A. Olshen, and C. J. Stone, *Classification and Regression Trees*, 1984.
- [3] D. A. Cieslak and N. V. Chawla, “A framework for monitoring classifiers’ performance: when and why failure occurs?” *Knowledge and Information Systems*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 83–108, 2009.
- [4] M. Fugate and J. R. Gattiker, “Anomaly detection enhanced classification in computer intrusion detection,” in *Pattern Recognition with Support Vector Machines*, vol. 2388, 2002, pp. 186–197.
- [5] M. Tavallaee, E. Bagheri, W. Lu, and A. A. Ghorbani, “A detailed analysis of the KDD CUP 99 data set,” in *IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence for Security and Defense Applications, CISDA 2009*, 2009.
- [6] J. McHugh, “Testing Intrusion detection systems: a critique of the 1998 and 1999 DARPA intrusion detection system evaluations as performed by Lincoln Laboratory,” *ACM Transactions on Information and System Security*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 262–294, 2000.
- [7] S. Sung, A.H. Mukkamala. “Identifying important features for intrusion detection using support vector machines and neural networks”. In *Proceedings of the Symposium on Applications and the Internet (SAINT)*, pp. 209–216. IEEE.
- [8] H. Kayacik, A. Zincir-Heywood and M. Heywood. “Selecting features for intrusion detection: A feature relevance analysis on KDD 99 intrusion detection datasets”. In *Proceedings of the Third Annual Conference on Privacy, Security and Trust (PST)*. 2005.
- [9] C. Lee, S. Shin and J. Chung. “Network intrusion detection through genetic feature selection”. In *Seventh ACIS International Conference on Software Engineering, Artificial Intelligence, Networking, and Parallel/Distributed Computing (SNPD)*, pp. 109–114. IEEE Computer Society, 2006.
- [10] H. Zhang and J.Su., “Naive Bayes for optimal ranking”, *Journal of Experimental and Theoretical Artificial Intelligence*. 2008, 20: 79-93.
- [11] Z. Muda, W. Yassin, M.N. Sulaiman, N.I. Udzir, “Intrusion Detection based on K-Means Clustering and Naïve Bayes Classification” 2011 7th International Conference on IT in Asia (CITA)”.
2011.
- [12] Weiming Hu, Steve Maybank, “AdaBoost-Based Algorithm for Network Intrusion Detection”. In *IEEE transaction on systems, MAN, and CYBERNETICS*, APRIL 2008.

AN EXPLORATION OF THE FACTORS AFFECTING USERS' SATISFACTION WITH MOBILE PAYMENTS

**Lisa Y. Chen and Wan-Ning Wu Department of Information Management,
I-Shou University, Taiwan**

ABSTRACT

Mobile payment allows consumers to make more flexible payments through convenient mobile devices. While mobile payment is easy and time save, the operation and security of mobile payment must ensure that the payment is fast, convenient, reliable and safety in order to increase the users' satisfaction. Therefore, this study based on technology acceptance model to explore the impact of external variables through perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on users' satisfaction. The data analysis methods used in this study are descriptive statistical analysis, reliability and validity analysis, Pearson correlation analysis and regression analysis to verify the hypotheses. The results show that all hypotheses are supported. However, mobile payment is still subject to many restrictions on development and there are limited related researches. The results of this study provided insight into the factors that affect the users' satisfaction for mobile payment. Related services development of mobile payment and future research suggestions are also offered.

KEYWORDS

Mobile Payment, Technology Acceptance Model, Users' satisfaction

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijcsit/V9N3/9317ijcsit08.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2017_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Lu, H. P. and Su, Y. J. (2009). "Factors affecting purchase intention on mobile shopping web sites," *Internet Research*, Vol.19, No. 4, pp. 442-458.
- [2] Zhang, R., Chen, J. Q., and Lee, C. J. (2013). "Mobile commerce and consumer privacy concerns," *The Journal of Computer Information Systems*, Vol. 53, No. 4, pp. 31-38.
- [3] Kim, C., Mirusmonov, M., and Lee, I. (2010). "An empirical examination of factors influencing the intention to use mobile payment," *Journal Computers in Human Behavior*, Vol. 26, No. 3, pp. 310- 322.
- [4] Nguyen, N., Cao, T. K., Dang, P. L. and Nguyen, H. A. (2016). "Predicting consumer intention to use mobile payment services: empirical evidence from Vietnam," *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 117-124.
- [5] Pousttchi, K. and Wiedemann, D. G. (2007). "What influences consumers' intention to use mobile payments?" Retrieved from: *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT)* Vol 9, No 3, June 2017 105 <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/a4dd/ce87edaa6d2bf14d0bd362e1c9beb24b030b.pdf> (March, 22, 2017).
- [6] Ondrus, J. and Pigneur, Y. (2007). "Cross-industry preferences for development of mobile payments in Switzerland," *Electronic Markets*, pp. 142-152.
- [7] Liébana-Cabanillas, F., Ramos de Luna, I., and Montoro-Ríos, F. (2017). "Intention to use new mobile payment systems: a comparative analysis of SMS and NFC payments," *Economic ResearchEkonomiska Istraživanja*, Vol. 30, No. 1, pp. 892-910.
- [8] Dornan, A. (2001). "The essential guide to wireless communications applications: from cellular systems to WAP and m-commerce," Upper Saddle River, NJ, Prentice Hall.
- [9] Heijden, H. (2002). "Factors affecting the successful introduction of mobile payment systems," *15th Bled Electronic Commerce Conference eReality: Constructing the eEconomy*, Bled, Slovenia, June 17-19, pp. 430-443.
- [10] Hahn I. and Kodó, K. (2017). "Mobile payment analysed from the aspects of Kano model." Retrieved from: <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1079862/FULLTEXT01.pdf> (March, 22, 2017).
- [11] Dahlberg, T., Mallat, N., Ondrus, J., and Zmijewska, A. (2008). "Past, present and future of mobile payments research: a literature review," *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, Vol. 7, No. 2, pp. 165-181.
- [12] Varshney, U. (2002). "Mobile payment," *IEEE Computer*, Vol. 35, No. 12, pp. 120-121.
- [13] Ondrus, J. and Pigneur, Y. (2006). "Towards a holistic analysis of mobile payments: a multiple perspectives approach," *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, Vol. 5, No. 3, pp. 246–257.
- [14] Sang, R. J. and Murdock, K. (2013). "Consumer acceptance of mobile marketing communications using the QR code," *Journal of Direct, Data and Digital Marketing Practice*, Vol. 15, No. 2, pp. 11-

- [15] Davis, F. D. (1989). "Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology," *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 13, No. 3, pp. 319-340.
- [16] Fishbein, M. and Ajzen, I. (1975). "Belief, attitude, intention, and behavior: an introduction to theory and research". Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.
- [17] Taylor, S. and Todd, P. (1995). "Assessing IT usage: the role of prior experience," *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 19, No. 4, pp. 561-570.
- [18] Gefen, D., Karahanna, E., and Straub, D. W. (2003), "Trust and TAM in online shopping: an integrated model," *MIS Quarterly*, Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 51-90.
- [19] Moon, J.W. and Kim, Y.G. (2001). "Extending the TAM for a world-wide-web context," *Information & Management*, Vol. 38, pp. 217-230.
- [20] Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F. (2000). "A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: four longitudinal field studies," *Management Science*, Vol. 46, No. 2, pp.186-204.
- [21] Brown, L. G. (1989). "The strategic and tactical implications of convenience in consumer product marketing," *The Journal of Consumer Marketing*, Vol. 6, No. 3, pp. 13-19.
- [22] Yoon, C. and Kim, S. (2007). "Convenience and TAM in a ubiquitous computing environment: the case of wireless LAN," *Electronic Commerce Research & Applications*, Vol. 6, No. 1, pp. 102-112.
- [23] Rogers, E.M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed.). New York: Free Press.
- [24] Craig, V.S., France, B., and Christie, L.C. (2004), "Factors influencing the adoption of web based shopping: the impact of trust," *ACM SIGMIS Database*, Vol. 35, No. 2, pp. 32-49.
- [25] Kim, E. and Tadisina, S. (2007). "A model of customers' trust in e-businesses: Micro-level inter-party trust formation," *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, Vol. 48, No. 1, pp. 88-104. [26] Kalakota, R. and Whinston, A. B. (1996). "Readings in Electronic Commerce" Addison-Wesley Publishing, Reading, MA.
- [27] Yoon, S. J. (2002). "The antecedents and consequences of trust in online-purchase decisions," *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, Vol. 16, No. 2, pp. 47-63.
- [28] Dahlberg, T., Mallat, N., and Öörni, A. (2003). Trust enhanced technology acceptance modelconsumer acceptance of mobile payment solutions: Tentative evidence, *Stockholm Mobility Roundtable*, 22-23. [29] Nunnally, J. C. (1978). "Psychometric theory," New York: McGraw-Hill.

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF LTE NETWORK USING MAXIMUM FLOW ALGORITHM

**Bir Bahadur Khatri¹, Bulbul Ahammad¹, Md. Mezbahul Islam², Rahmina Rubaiat²
and Md. Imdadul Islam¹**

**¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Jahangirnagar University, Savar,
Dhaka, Bangladesh**

²Department of Computer Science and Engineering, MBSTU, Tangail, Bangladesh

ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a new traffic flow model of the Long Term Evaluation (LTE) network for the Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access Network (E-UTRAN). Here only one Evolve Node B (eNB) nearest to the Mobility Management Entity (MME) and Serving Gateway (S-GW) will use the S1 link to bridge the E-UTRAN and Evolved Packet Core (EPC). All the eNBs of a tracking area will be connected to each other by the X2 link. Determination of capacity of a link of such a network is a challenging job since each node offers its own traffic and at the same time conveys traffic of other nodes. In this paper, we apply maximum flow algorithm including superposition theorem to solve the traffic flow of radio network. Using the total flow per subcarrier, a new traffic model is also developed in the paper. The relation among the traffic parameters: 'blocking probability', 'offered traffic', 'instantaneous capacity', 'average holding time', and 'number of users' are shown graphically under both QPSK and 16-QAM. The concept of the network will be helpful to improve the SINR of the received signal of eNBs located long distance relative to MME/S-GW.

KEYWORDS

Aggregate offered traffic, blocking probability, traffic channel, weighted graph and RB.

For More Details : <http://aircconline.com/ijcsit/V12N4/12420ijcsit06.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2020_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Jesmin Akhter, Abu Sayed Md. MostafizurRahaman, Md. Imdadul Islam, M. R. Amin, 'Traffic Modelling of Low Dense Femtocellular Network for Long Term Evolution,' Journal of Computer and Communications, pp.88-101, Vol.7, No.12, December 2019
- [2] Ma Lin, Wei Shouming and Qiang Wei, 'A Novel Traffic Analysis Method For PoC over LTE Based on Retrial Calling Model,' 2011 6th International ICST Conference on Communications and Networking in China (CHINACOM), 17-19 Aug. 2011, pp.771-774, Harbin, China
- [3] H. Hidayat, Al KautsarPermana, I. Ridwany, and Iskandar, 'Cell Capacity Prediction with Traffic Load Effect for Soft Frequency Reuse (SFR) Technique in LTE – A Network,' The 11th International Conference on Telecommunication Systems, Services, and Applications, 26-27 Oct. 2017, 26-27 October 2017, Lombok-Indonesia
- [4] Haka, V. Aleksieva and H. Valchanov, 'Comparative Analysis of Traffic Prioritisation Algorithms by LTE Base Station Scheduler,' 2020 21st International Symposium on Electrical Apparatus & Technologies (SIELA), pp. 1-4, 3-6 June 2020, Bourgas, Bulgaria
- [5] M. Sahu, 'Delay Jitter Analysis for Uplink Traffic in LTE Systems,' 2019 11th International Conference on Communication Systems & Networks (COMSNETS), pp. 504-506, 7-11 Jan. 2019, Bengaluru, India
- [6] R. Liu, Q. Chen, G. Yu, G. Y. Li and Z. Ding, 'Resource Management in LTE-U Systems: Past, Present, and Future,' IEEE Open Journal of Vehicular Technology, vol. 1, pp. 1-17, Oct' 2020
- [7] Bulbul Ahammad, Risala T. Khan and Md. Imdadul Islam, 'WLAN -LTE Integrated Traffic Model under Unlicensed Spectrum,' International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security (IJCSIS), vol. 17, no. 3, pp.85-100, March 2019
- [8] Fatima Sapundzhi and Metodi Popstoilov, 'C# implementation of the maximum flow problem,' 2019 27th National Conference with International Participation (TELECOM), pp. 62-65, 30-31 Oct. 2019, Sofia, Bulgaria
- [9] Y. Wang, J. Ling, S. Zhou, Y. Liu, W. Liao and B. Zhang, 'A Study on Rapid Incremental Maximum Flow Algorithm in Dynamic Network,' 2018 1st International Cognitive Cities Conference (IC3), pp.7-11, 7-9 Aug. 2018, Okinawa, Japan
- [10] Jiyang Dong, Wei Li, Congbo Cai, Zhong Chen, 'Draining Algorithm for the Maximum Flow Problem,' 2009 International Conference on Communications and Mobile Computing, pp.197-200, 6-8 Jan. 2009, Yunnan, China
- [11] Ruipeng Bai, HuiGuo, Zhenzhong Wang, Yanlong Zhang, Fan Zhang and Lei Chen, 'FPGA Interconnect Resources Test Based on A Improved Ford- Fulkerson Algorithm,' 2018 IEEE 4th Information Technology and Mechatronics Engineering Conference (ITOEC 2018), pp.251-258, 14-16 Dec. 2018, Chongqing, China
- [12] Jesmin Akhter, Md. Imdadul Islam, ASM M Rahaman and M R Amin, 'Performance Evaluation of Femtocell Based LTE Network under the Concept of Cross- layer Optimization,' International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, pp. 52-60, vol. 14, no. 7, July 2016

- [13] Jesmin Akhter, Md. Imdadul Islam, ASM M Ra haman and M R Amin, 'The MIMO Performance of LTE Network under Rayleigh Fading Environment,' International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, pp. 88-94, vol. 14, no. 8, August 2016
- [14] Lifeng Zhao and Xiaowan Meng, 'An Improved Algorithm for Solving Maximum Flow Problem,' 2012 8th International Conference on Natural Computation (ICNC 2012), pp.1016-1018, 29-31 May 2012, Chongqing, China
- [15] Bo Hong and Zhengyu He, 'An Asynchronous Multithreaded Algorithm for the Maximum Network Flow Problem with Nonblocking Global Relabeling Heuristic,' IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed Systems, pp.1025-1033, vol. 22, no. 6, June 2011
- [16] Ali Mustafa Elshawesh, Mohamed Abdulali, 'Dimensioning of Circuit Switched Networks by using Simulation Code based on Erlang (B) formula,' 2014 Global Summit on Computer & Information Technology (GSCIT), pp. 1-5, 14-16 June 2014, Sousse, Tunisia
- [17] James K. Tamgno, Mamadou Alpha Barry, Simplic E. Gngang, Claude Lishou, 'Estimating Number of Organs using Erlang's B & C-Formulas,' 2017 19th International Conference on Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT), pp.858-864, 19-22 Feb. 2017, Bongpyeong, South Korea

RISK MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORKS FOR CLOUD COMPUTING: A CRITICAL REVIEW

Rana Alosaimi¹ and Mohammad Alnuem²

Department of Information Systems, King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

ABSTRACT

Cloud computing technology has experienced exponential growth over the past few years. It provides many advantages for both individuals and organizations. However, at the same time, many issues have arisen due to the vast growth of cloud computing. Organizations often have concerns about the migration and utilization of cloud computing due to the loss of control over their outsourced resources and cloud computing is vulnerable to risks. Thus, a cloud provider needs to manage the cloud computing environment risks in order to identify, assess, and prioritize the risks in order to decrease those risks, improve security, increase confidence in cloud services, and relieve organizations' concerns on the issue of using a cloud environment. Considering that a conventional risk management framework does not fit well with cloud computing due to the complexity of its environment, research in this area has become widespread. The aim of this paper is to review the previously proposed risk management frameworks for cloud computing and to make a comparison between them in order to determine the strengths and weaknesses of each of them. The review will consider the extent of the involvement and participation of consumers in cloud computing and other issues.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing; Risk Management & Information Security

For More Details : <https://airconline.com/ijcsit/V8N4/8416ijcsit01.pdf>

Volume Link : http://airccse.org/journal/ijcsit2016_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Charanya, M. Aramudhan, K. Mohan, S. Nithya, "Levels of Security Issues in Cloud Computing," *International Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 2013.
- [2] M. Alzain, B. Soh, E. Pardede, "A Survey on Data Security Issues in Cloud Computing: From Single to Multi-Clouds," *Journal of Software*, 2013.
- [3] L. Qian, Z. Luo, Y. Du, and L. Guo, "Cloud Computing: An Overview," M. Jaatun, G. Zhao, & C. Rong, *Cloud Computing*, pp. 626-631. Berlin: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2009.
- [4] R. Bhadauria, and S. Sanyal, "Survey on Security Issues in Cloud Computing and Associated Mitigation Techniques," *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 2012.
- [5] A. Apostu, F. Puican, G. Ularu, G. Suci, and G. Todoran, "Study on advantages and disadvantages of Cloud Computing – the advantages of Telemetry Applications in the Cloud," *Recent Advances in Applied Computer Science and Digital Services*, 2013.
- [6] A. Apostu, F. Puican, G. Ularu, G. Suci, G. Todoran, "Study on advantages and disadvantages of Cloud Computing – the advantages of Telemetry Applications in the Cloud," *Recent Advances in Applied Computer Science and Digital Services*, 2013.
- [7] M. Hölbl, "Cloud Computing Security and Privacy Issues," *The Council of European Professional Informatics Societies*, 2011.
- [8] G. Tucker, and C. Li, "Cloud Computing Risks," *Proceedings on the International Conference on Internet Computing*, 2012.
- [9] T. Chou, "Security Threats on Cloud Computing Vulnerabilities," *International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology*, 2013.
- [10] M. Ryan, "Cloud computing security: the scientific challenge, and a survey of solutions," *Journal of Systems and Software*, 2013.
- [11] S. Zhang, S. Zhang, X. Chen, and X. Huo, "Cloud Computing Research and Development Trend," *Second International Conference on Future Networks*, 2010.
- [12] M. Ali, S. Khan, A. Vasilakos, "Security in cloud computing: Opportunities and challenges," *Informatics and Computer Science Intelligent Systems Applications*, 2015.
- [13] F. Ahamed, S. Shahrestani, A. Ginige, "Cloud Computing: Security and Reliability Issues," *IBIMA*, 2013.
- [14] P. Sareen, "Cloud Computing: Types, Architecture, Applications, Concerns, Virtualization and Role of IT Governance in Cloud," *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, 2013.
- [15] I. Ashraf, "An Overview of Service Models of Cloud Computing," *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research*, 2014.
- [16] G. Kulkarni, P. Chavan, H. Bankar, K. Koli, and V. Waykule, "A new approach to Software as Service Cloud," *7th International Conference on Telecommunication Systems, Services, and Applications*, 2012.

- [17] J. Gibson, D. Eveleigh, R. Rondeau, and Q. Tan, "Benefits and Challenges of Three Cloud Computing Service Models," Fourth International Conference on Computational Aspects of Social Networks, 2012.
- [18] W. Hsu, "Conceptual Framework of Cloud Computing Governance Model - An Education Perspective," IEEE Technology and Engineering Education, 2012.
- [19] R. Sharma, R. Trivedi, "Literature review: Cloud Computing –Security Issues, Solution and Technologies," International Journal of Engineering Research, 2014.
- [20] F. Liu, J. Tong, J. Mao, R. Bohn, J. Messina, L. Badger, and D. Leaf, "NIST Cloud Computing Reference Architecture," National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2011.
- [21] A. Gajbhiye, and K. Shrivastva, "Cloud Computing: Need, Enabling Technology, Architecture, Advantages and Challenges," Confluence The Next Generation Information Technology Summit, 2014.
- [22] H. Berg, "Risk Management: Procedures, Methods and Experiences," Bundesamt für Strahlenschutz, Salzgitter, Germany, 2010.
- [23] ISO/Guide 73, "Risk Management-Vocabulary," International Organization for Standardisation, 2009.
- [24] G. Dickson, "Principles of Risk Management," Glasgow Caledonian University, 1995.
- [25] G. Stoneburner, A. Goguen, and A. Feringa, "NIST SP 800-30 Risk Management Guide for Information Technology Systems," pp. 8-26, NIST, 2002.
- [26] "A Risk Management Standard," The Institute of Risk Management (AIRMIC) and The Public Risk Management Association (Alarm), 2002.
- [27] P. Saripalli, and B. Walters, "A Quantitative Impact and Risk Assessment Framework for Cloud Security," IEEE 3rd International Conference on Cloud Computing, pp. 280-288, IEEE, 2010.
- [28] S. Tanimoto, M. Hiramoto, M. Iwashita, H. Sato, and A. Kanai, "Risk Management on the Security Problem in Cloud Computing," First ACIS/JNU International Conference on Computers, Networks, Systems, and Industrial Engineering, pp. 147-152, IEEE, 2011.
- [29] J. Fito, M. Macías, and J. Guitart, "Toward Business-driven Risk Management for Cloud Computing," Network and Service Management (CNSM), pp. 238-241, IEEE, 2010.
- [30] X. Zhang, N. Wuwong, H. Li, and X. Zhang, "Information Security Risk Management Framework for the Cloud Computing Environments," IEEE International Conference on Computer and Information Technology, pp. 1328-1334, IEEE, 2010.
- [31] M. Almorsy, J. Grundy, and A. Ibrahim, "Collaboration-Based Cloud Computing Security Management Framework," IEEE 4th International Conference on Cloud Computing, pp. 364-371, IEEE, 2011.
- [32] F. Xie, Y. Peng, W. Zhao, D. Chen, X. Wang, and X. Huo, "A Risk Management Framework For Cloud Computing," IEEE 2nd International Conference, pp. 476-480, IEEE, 2012.

- [33] S. Albakri, B. Shanmugam, G. Samy, N. Idris, and A. Ahmed, "Security risk assessment framework for cloud computing environments," Security and Communication Networks, Wiley Online Library, 2014.
- [34] H. Linstone, and M. Turoff, "The Delphi Method: Techniques and Applications," Addison-Wesley, 1975.
- [35] FERMA, "FERMA's Risk Management Standard," 2003, Retrieved from [http://www.ferma.eu/Portals/2/documents/RMS/RMS-UK\(2\).pdf](http://www.ferma.eu/Portals/2/documents/RMS/RMS-UK(2).pdf) International Journal of Computer Science & Information Technology (IJCSIT) Vol 8, No 4, August 2016 11
- [36] E. Humphreys, "Implementing the ISO/IEC 27001 Information Security Management System Standard," Artech Print on Demand, 2007.
- [37] J. Miller, L. Candler, and H. Wald, "Information Security Governance Government Considerations for the Cloud Computing Environment," Booz Allen Hamilton, pp. 4-11, 2009.
- [38] NIST, "Standards for Security Categorization of Federal Information and Information Systems," FIPS-199, 2002, Retrieved from <http://csrc.nist.gov/publications/fips/fips199/FIPS-PUB-199-final.pdf>

ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING AND CONTROLLING SYSTEM FOR MUSHROOM FARM WITH ONLINE INTERFACE

Arjuna Marzuki and Soh Yan Ying

**School of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang,
Malaysia**

ABSTRACT

Agriculture sensors play an important role in modern agriculture. The use of sensors in various agriculture sectors minimizes the environmental impact on crops, helps in increasing yield and saving cost of operation. Among all agriculture industries in Malaysia, the mushroom industry is a comparatively new and small. As most of the mushroom farms in Malaysia are small-scaled, their production capability is limited by inadequate environmental control system and the lack of financial resources to upgrade the systems. This paper presents an environmental monitoring and controlling system to monitor and control the environmental conditions in a mushroom farm. It enables user to monitor temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide concentration and light intensity in a mushroom farm on an android device by using ThingSpeak online platform. The control algorithm is able to control devices in a mushroom farm automatically based on feedback from the sensors to maintain the environment in an optimum condition for mushroom growth. The measured percentage error of temperature, humidity, carbon dioxide and the light using the developed system was as low as 0.4%, 1.5%, 2.2% and 1.34% respectively

KEYWORDS

Agriculture, Interface Circuit, Internet of Things, Monitoring and Control, Sensor, Wireless.

For More Details : <https://aireconline.com/iicsit/V9N4/9417iicsit02.pdf>

Volume Link : https://aircse.org/journal/iicsit2017_curr.html

REFERENCES

- [1] Unit Pengurusan Prestasi dan Pelaksanaan (2010) Economic Transformation Programme: A Roadmap for Malaysia (1 Malaysia). Performance Management and Delivery Unit, Jabatan Perdana Menteri.
- [2] Istikomah Qurat-ul-Ain., & Dahlan A. R. A, (2015) “The Transformation of Agriculture Based Economy to an Industrial Sector through Crowd Sourcing In Malaysia”, *Int. J. Comput. Sci. Inf. Technol. Res.*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp.34–41.
- [3] Bakar B.B., (2009) “The Malaysian Agricultural Industry in the New Millennium – Issues and Challenges,” pp. 337–356.
- [4] Rosmiza M., Davies W., Aznie R. C., Jabil M., & Mazdi M, (2016) “Prospects for Increasing Commercial Mushroom Production in Malaysia: Challenges and Opportunities”, *Mediterr. J. Soc. Sci.*, Vol. 7, No. 1, pp. 406–415.
- [5] Haimid M. T., Rahim H., & Dardak R. A, (2013) “Understanding the mushroom industry and its marketing strategies for fresh produce in Malaysia”, *Econ. Technol. Manag. Rev.*, Vol. 8, pp. 27–37.
- [6] Mat Amin M. Z., & Harun A, (2015) “Competitiveness of the Mushroom Industry in Malaysia” [Online]. Available: http://ap.fttc.agnet.org/ap_db.php?id=481&print=1. [Accessed: 18-Oct-2016].
- [7] Australian Mushroom Growers Association, “Introduction to Mushroom Growing,” AMGA, pp. 1-16.
- [8] Van Nieuwenhuijzen, Bram., & Oei, P (2005) Small-scale mushroom cultivation oyster, shiitake and wood ear mushrooms, *Agrodok;40*. Agromisa/CTA, Wageningen, The Netherlands.
- [9] Stamets P., & Chilton, J. S, (1983) “The Mushroom Cultivator: A Practical Guide to Growing Mushrooms at Home”, *S. Cal. L. Rev.*, p. 416.
- [10] Grant, J.J (2002) An investigation of the airflow in mushroom growing structures, the development of an improved, three-dimensional solution technique for fluid flow and its evaluation for the modelling of mushroom growing structures. PhD thesis, Dublin City University.
- [11] Kwon H., & Kim, B. S (2004) *Mushroom Grow. Handb.* 1, pp. 192–196.
- [12] Tisdale T. E (2004) Cultivation of the Oyster Mushroom (*Pleurotus* sp.) on Wood Substrates in Hawaii. MSc thesis, University of Hawai’i.
- [13] Wang X., (2014) “Temperature and Humidity Monitoring System Based on GSM Module”, *International Journal of Computer, Consumer and Control.*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 41–49.
- [14] Rahali A., Guerbaoui M., Ed-dahhak A., El Afou Y., Tannouche A., Lachhab A., &

Bouchikhi, B, (2011) “Development of a data acquisition and greenhouse control system based on GSM”, *Int. J. Eng. Sci. Technol.*, Vol. 3, No. 8, pp. 297–306.

- [15] Kalinin Y. S., Velikov E. K., & Markova, V. I, (2015) “Design of Indoor Environment Monitoring System Using Arduino”, *Int. J. Innov. Sci. Mod. Eng.*, Vol. 3, No. 7, pp. 46–49, 20.
- [16] Lokesh Krishna K., Madhuri J., & Anuradha K, (2016) “A ZigBee based Energy Efficient Environmental Monitoring Alerting and Controlling System”, in *International Conference On Information Communication And Embedded Systems (ICICES2016)*.